

THE WORK AND PLACE OF USTA OLIM KOMILOV IN THE FIELD**Jo‘rayev Azamat Yusuf o‘g‘li**

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Annotation: This article covered the life and work of the Usta Olim Komilov.

Keywords: percussion, national, dance, circle, folk, melody, culture, melody, folklore, art, instrument, pedagogue, sound, stage, music, school, performance.

In the musical practice of Eastern peoples, including Uzbekistan, percussion instruments occupy a very important place. In the development of Uzbek national art, one of the types of instruments embedded in the hearts of the people is the circle. It is one of the percussion instruments in Uzbekistan, and is distinguished from other instruments by its impressiveness. The circle is a leading solo instrument in Uzbek musical art, among the people, in addition to being a brass instrument on stage. Especially in the art of dance, the main task has been fulfilled and is coming. In the performance of a folk dance tune, the circle can be seen to be clearly distinguished from its richness and complexity, impressiveness, usefulness, serjeality in Solo Performance.

Forming a school of performing dance art with a circle, this artist first perfected Uzbek folk methods in the 1930s to create a “circle lesson” i.e. a “double applause”. Created by master scholar Kornilov, it became the basis of the Uzbek School of dance art, as a result of the methods by which bora-bora was perfected and adapted to dance movements, the “Qosh-Kars” noted above was later called The “Circle lesson”.

Usta Olim Komilov was born in Margilon in 1875 in the family of a weaver-craftsman. Having lost his parents early, Olimjon is forced from the age of 10 to work by entering a master-room where he prepares a cart. This way you will have to live for

several years. It was only in the evenings that the music he would go to weddings and listen to there without letting anyone know gave him joy. At that time, the art of Circle performance was spreading a wide ear. Olimjon doyra's magic tattoos evoked pleasure from an early age. Immediately after his break from work, he takes his doyras into his hands and begins to return his methods, which are preserved in his memory. The services of Masaid the father, a well-known Circle man, are invaluable in the development of olimjon as a skilled musician. He teaches the young talent his own unique subtle ways and secrets of playing a circle. In addition to the circle, Olimjon also perfectly learned to play chang, Nagora and dutor. In the performance of the circle, his talent was manifested brighter. The circle in which he played was of particular influence. His Echoes would have been distinctive and influential. The performer of the instrument was distinguished from others by its rhythmic accuracy, the colorfulness of dynamic and timbre paints, and the exuberant and unique sound freshness. In 1918, he began to form musical amateur artistic teams in various organizations in Margilan, with which he began to give concerts in tea rooms and villages, and attracted talented young people to come and join this ensemble. During that period, it was able to attract more than 20 young people. They, in turn, achieved the level of professional musicians in the future. In 1926, Olim Komilov, together with the famous Yusupjon interesting, got a job in the concert-ethnographic ensemble organized by Muhiddinqori Yakubov. Later this ensemble is joined by Tamarakhanim and for several years has been engaged in creative activities together with the master Olim Komilov. After a year, they go on tour in the cities of Moscow, Leningrad and Baku and enjoy a large number of listeners with rich examples of Uzbek folk creativity. In 1930, the ensemble was reorganized and transformed into the Uzbek state musical theater. O.Komilov also goes with these theater artists to the Olympics of people's creativity, which will be held in Moscow. Mrs. Tamara and Mukarram Turgunboyeva perform "Daro-madi flower game", "Big Game", "Ufori sabo" dance and win the audience's applause. During 1931-1934, O.Komilov begins to collect methods created by the people, which are being forgotten.

To carry out this work, his mentors Masaid ota and Yusup rely on the help of the curious and, as a result, manage to assemble several dozen colorful techniques. Master O.Komilov also made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek dance art. Together with Mrs. Tamara, she was able to create new Uzbek dances “Zang”, “Flower game”, “Sadr”. O. in the staging of dances in Uzbek musical performances. Kamilov's contributions are invaluable. The largest postcards of the 1930s - V.Uspensky and G.Mushel's "Farkhad and sweet", R.The dances in glière's musical drama “Gulsara ” are exactly those of Master O.Created and staged by Komilov. In return for his productive work, he was awarded the title of “hero of Labor” in 1932. In 1935, O.Komilov was invited to the International Dance Festival in London by Mrs. Tamara, A.Ismailov and T.Together with the jalilovs, he took part in the “gold medal”. The master's pupil, Odil Kamolkhozhaev, remembered his teacher, saying - “in 1935, Queen Elizabeth of England became obsessed with the execution of the circle of the master scientist Komilov. The paw print of the prodigy was moved to the hook and placed in the UK Art Museum, where it remains today,” he said.

Usta Olim Komilov kept many methods in his memory. Many of their parts are part of I.Akbarov, V.Uspensky, E.Recorded by the Romanovskaya. I.What was written by Akbarov was published in a collection called “Doyra methods”. The collection included 47 folk methods and several rhythmic compositions.¹ The world-recognized circle, the connoisseur of Uzbek dance art, was always surrounded by disciples. During his many years of pedagogical activity, he prepared many talented musicians, for the prosperity of the Performing Arts of the circle in Uzbekistan, as well as for the continuation of his work. Toychi Inagomov, Ghafir Azimov, Abulkosim Toychiyev, Ghafir Solikhov were among them. He was awarded the title “Honored artist of Uzbekistan”, referring to his many years of creative and pedagogical activity.

¹ A.TAshmatova “Ijrochilik san’ati tarixi” musiqa oliy ta’lim muassasalari uchun darslik “Musiqqa” nashriyoti. Toshkent – 2017.

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